

Lattice Energies in Relation to Coefficients of Thermal Expansion of Alkali Metal Halides

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A general relation involving the lattice energy, U_0 , and coefficient of cubical thermal expansion, α , has been proposed for solid alkali metal halides. The statistical analysis to the concerned data appears to support the average values of $U_0\alpha \approx 0.021$ kcal mole⁻¹ deg⁻¹. On the basis of established relation, the α values of francium halides are predicted.

THE lattice energy, U_0 , of predominantly ionic compounds takes into account the overall attractive and repulsive forces operating in the crystal lattices. Since most of the properties of such solids do depend fundamentally on these ionic interactions, it appears reasonable to expect either a direct or indirect dependence of lattice energy on some appropriate crystal properties. It is probably on this logic that the U_0 data for a family of similar ionic solids appear to explain their several observed physicochemical trends. The solid alkali metal halides, being a suitable family of this interest, have been a subject of study¹⁻⁵ from this view point. The Born-Haber cycle relates the lattice or crystal energy of an ionic solid to other thermochemical data. Moreover, the thermal property viz., the coefficient of cubical expansion, α , is an important guide to understand the compactness of ionic compounds, in general. It was, therefore, thought instructive to investigate a possible relationship between U_0 and α in case of crystalline alkali metal halides which appears to lack so far. The present communication records an attempt in this direction.

Results and Discussion

Using the lattice energy equation per mole of a simple ionic crystal,

$$U_0 = \frac{Az_+z_-e^2N}{r_0} \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right) \quad \dots (1)$$

it has been shown earlier⁵ that the product U_0r_0 is approximately constant for solid 1:1 alkali metal halides [besides other constants in eqn. (1), A and n being assumed very nearly equal].

i.e., $U_0r_0 \approx \text{constant}$

$$\text{or } U_0 \propto \frac{1}{r_0} \quad \dots (2)$$

A parallel conclusion⁶ in case of these halides appears to support the trend.

Since the equilibrium interionic distance, r_0 , and the coefficient of expansion, α , are mutually related to cohesive forces in similar ionic lattices, it seems, therefore, reasonable to assume

$$r_0 \propto \alpha \quad \dots (3)$$

Taking into consideration eqns. (2) and (3),

$$U_0 \propto \frac{1}{\alpha} \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\text{or } U_0 \alpha \approx \text{constant} \quad \dots (5)$$

The validity of eqn. (5) has been examined from the available data on lattice energy⁷, U_0 , and coefficients of expansion⁸, α , for several halides of alkali metals.

TABLE 1—RELATION BETWEEN U_0 AND α FOR SOLID ALKALI METAL HALIDES

Alkali halide*	U_0^* kcal mol ⁻¹	$\alpha \times 10^5$ deg ⁻¹	$U_0\alpha$ kcal mol ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹
NaF	217	10.8	0.023
NaCl	184	12.8	0.022
NaBr	176	12.9	0.023
NaI	165	14.4	0.024
KF	192	11.1	0.021
KCl	168	11.4	0.019
KBr	161	12.0	0.019
KI	152	13.5	0.020
RbF	185	11.5	0.021
RbCl	163	10.8	0.018
RbBr	157	11.4	0.018
RbI	148	12.9	0.019
CsF	176	9.6	0.017
CsCl	157	15.0	0.024
CsBr	151	18.0	0.027
CsI	144	16.5	0.024

*Lithium halides are excluded since a significant higher trend of $U_0\alpha$ is observed on account their appreciable covalent character as compared to other alkali halides.

**The three different sets of U_0 data, mentioned under ref. 7, give the same average values of $U_0\alpha \approx 0.021$. More reliable set of U_0 values, derived from B-H cycle has been utilized.

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Table 1 shows an approximate constancy of the product $U_0\alpha$ in case of different alkali halides. The average value of $U_0\alpha \approx 0.021 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$ appears to agree satisfactorily with the individual $U_0\alpha$ obtained for most of the companion halides. It is thus clear that the concerned salts consisting of ionic constituents are in a similar state of mutual interaction towards the thermal effect in observing nearly equal $U_0\alpha$ products in general.

Alternatively, it appears from a general consideration that higher the absolute melting point, T_m , of the halide of a given alkali metal, the tighter is the binding and smaller the coefficient of thermal expansion, α . In other words different halide members should show a near constancy of αT_m . The mean numerical value of $\alpha T_m \approx 0.126$ in the concerned family indeed justifies this assumption⁹. The replacement of T_m by U_0 (since U_0/T_m is fairly constant for solid alkali metal halides²) in the aforesaid relation tends to give a plausible support to the constancy of $U_0\alpha$, as is evident from Table 1. Moreover, it is interesting to note that the ratio of observed $U_0\alpha$ and αT_m in the present work gives $U_0/T_m \approx 0.167$ which matches with the $U_0/T_m \approx 0.165 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$, reported² earlier for the family of alkali metal halides.

The genuinity of the proposed relation, $U_0\alpha \approx 0.021 \text{ k cal mol}^{-1} \text{ deg}^{-1}$ has been further tested by the use of statistical approach (regression analysis) to the relevant data. Assuming a general type of linear relationship between U_0 and $\frac{1}{\alpha}$, the derived equation of the most probable line is

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = 58.7 U_0 - 1848 \quad \dots (6)$$

where the regression coefficient is 58.7 and the standard error ± 8.24 . The value of correlation coefficient (0.88) indicates an appropriate nature of the relationship.

Using the relations (5) and (6), the coefficients of expansion, α , of francium halides have been estimated from their lattice energy¹⁰, U_0 , data. The α values, thus obtained, are shown in Table 2.

The corresponding α data for francium halides, calculated from the two relations, appear to agree meaningfully. It may be seen from Table 2 that

TABLE 2—ESTIMATED α VALUES IN CASE OF SOLID FRANCIUM HALIDES

Francium halide	U_0 kcal mol ⁻¹	$\alpha^* \times 10^6$ deg ⁻¹
FrF	171	12.3 (12.2)
FrCl	151	13.9 (14.2)
FrBr	146	14.4 (14.9)
FrI	139	15.1 (15.8)
FrAt	137	15.3 (16.1)

* α estimates obtained from the statistically derived equation are shown in parentheses.

with an increasing trend of equilibrium interionic distance¹¹, r_0 , among the francium halides, the coefficients of cubical expansion, α , tend to increase in accordance with the general experimental observations⁸ on other alkali metal halides (Table 1). This is what one should expect in view of the growing weakening of interionic attraction from FrF to FrAt. A similar behaviour also holds good for the solid alkali metal astatides.

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